

Towards an Easy-to-Use Machine Learning Framework for Cultural Heritage Scientists

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Abstract

Cultural heritage artifacts are invaluable records of human history and identity, offering unique insights into past societies, traditions, and innovations that shape our understanding of cultural evolution and continuity. Over the years, numerous factors have led to their deterioration and damage, highlighting the critical need for assessment and protective strategies to guarantee their continued preservation. As breakthroughs in Machine Learning and other Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) continue to advance, there is a growing potential for such tools to support cultural heritage scientists (conservators, archaeologists, museologists, etc.) in such an endeavor. A framework encompassing a suite of related tools can enable researchers across disciplines, including those with limited technical expertise, to have access to complex data analysis and preservation tasks. To validate the system's effectiveness, we successfully deployed multiple trials on a subset of the ZJU-Leaper dataset, confirming the framework's ability to streamline such segmentation workflows. Our contribution is an open-source framework offering a user-friendly interface that allows users to upload, process and manage their machine learning projects, with minimal or no prior technical knowledge needed. The framework as presented here supports semantic segmentation tasks, enabling projects with such needs to utilize state-of-the-art machine learning models effortlessly.

Keywords: Cultural Heritage, Artifact Examination, Machine Learning Framework, Machine Learning Operations (MLOps), Semantic Segmentation

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Introduction

The continuous development of machine learning algorithms has led to significant achievements in various fields, such as computer vision. With an increasing demand for process automation, more and more applications are using such algorithms (Shinde and Shah, 2018), making these technologies an essential component of modern approaches, while, for the same reason, nowadays there exists a multitude of tools and frameworks to build, develop and deploy applications supporting such operations (Berberi et al., 2025). From a cultural heritage perspective, the analysis of artifacts is often a time-consuming task as it requires the consideration and examination of multiple aspects of its properties, whether drawn from visual observation or historical analysis (Ding and Liang, 2024). Computer vision algorithms can address some of these challenges by accelerating the inspection process, thus replacing manual serial checks with automatic detection (Carrilho et al., 2024). Such methods have already proven effective in diverse heritage contexts, ranging from the automated identification of structural cracks in cultural heritage images (Huang et al., 2025) to the digital analysis of degraded ancient manuscripts (Hanif et al., 2023).

However, such technologies often demand specialized technical expertise, making them less accessible to non-expert researchers. To overcome this issue, we have developed an easy-to-use machine learning framework that simplifies the interaction with these technologies. We propose that a modular layer with a user-friendly interface can enable non-technical researchers to perform machine learning tasks more easily than using the core tools directly. To showcase the framework's capabilities, in this paper we present the use-case of the fabric defect segmentation problem, where the objective is to identify damaged areas in textile pictures. In summary, the main contributions of this work are:

- **Platform Architecture:** The design of an extensible framework that abstracts the process complexity, providing an intuitive environment for users to easily navigate and interact with machine learning operations.
- **End-to-End Workflow:** The integration of a comprehensive pipeline supporting the entire machine learning lifecycle, seamlessly connecting data annotation, model training, and inference, within a unified environment.

The structure of this paper is as follows: Section 2 briefly refers to the related work around the technologies employed to build the proposed framework and the fabric defect segmentation task. Section 3 describes the framework's architecture and the steps that compose each machine learning project pipeline. Finally, Section 4 summarizes the work presented here with its benefits as well as its limitations and outlines potential directions for future work to enhance the platform's functionality.

Related work

End-to-end machine learning platforms

As the applications of machine learning are constantly growing in diversity and complexity, users tend to prefer all-in-one solutions that can automate their workflow, as it can save important time while performing a complex task. The Intel Geti platform (Intel Geti 2023) allows its users to add images or video data, make annotations, train, export and optimize AI models for deployment through an intuitive graphical interface. The platform supports a wide range of

computer vision tasks, such as image segmentation and classification, object detection, anomaly detection, and keypoint detection. When handling advanced tasks, as many recent applications require task combination, Intel Geti provides support for task chaining. Regarding its architecture, Geti is highly modular, with each core service implemented as a separate component. Moreover, it is equipped with state-of-the-art technologies, such as active learning and smart annotations that speed up labor-intensive tasks while also integrating seamlessly with Intel's OpenVINO toolkit, enabling hardware-aware optimizations. Although this platform is feature-complete, it seems more targeted to individuals or teams with experience in Machine Learning (ML) processes and pipelines who are looking to optimize their workflow, while non-technical users would prefer a more simplified interface, which they can navigate and operate with minimal effort.

Fabric defect segmentation

Semantic segmentation is a computer vision task that assigns a class label to every pixel primarily using a deep learning algorithm. The first work to apply convolutional neural networks for semantic segmentation was Fully Convolutional Networks (FCN) (Long et al., 2015). Especially for fabric defect segmentation, Tabernik et al. (2020) proposed a two-stage convolutional network that demonstrates effective learning with a small number of defective samples. Building on the success of transformers (Vaswani et al., 2017) in natural language processing, Vision Transformers (Dosovitskiy et al., 2020) have emerged as state-of-the-art models for semantic segmentation, including the fabric defect segmentation. Architectures such as HKAN (Li et al., 2024), which combines CNNs, transformers and KANs (Liu et al., 2024) to capture both local and global features, and the Swin-Unet with Gabor filter-based approach (Xu et al., 2023) which enhances low-level texture feature extraction, have shown promising results in this task. For the purposes of this paper, we focus specifically on binary segmentation, where each pixel is classified as either defective or non-defective.

Data annotation platforms

In supervised machine learning, particularly in computer vision, annotated data are crucial for training models to map inputs to desired outputs. Among the different annotation types, pixel-level image segmentation is notably more labor intensive than simpler methods such as bounding boxes (Reza et al., 2025), as the first incorporates more complex shapes, called segments, typically defined as polygonal regions via a sequence of points on the image. CVAT (CVAT.ai Corporation, 2023) is a widely adopted annotation tool that supports complex tasks, such as image annotation for segmentation, classification and object detection, video annotation, and even 3D point cloud labeling. It provides a wide set of selection tools for detailed annotation of regions of interest, while its Python SDK (Software Development Kit) allows for an easy integration with any Python framework such as Django, Flask and FastAPI, making it an easy-to-go choice for scalable annotation pipelines. For the above reasons, CVAT was selected to support both current and future needs of our work, as, for example, it can support potential expansions into 3D data. Other popular platform choices that should be mentioned are Labelme (Wada, 2021) and Label Studio (Tkachenko et al., 2020), both with multiple features and data type integrations, but seemingly more suitable for simpler or more lightweight annotation tasks.

Machine Learning Operations (MLOps)

Since machine learning operations may vary and require different customizations depending on the project or be deployed across a diverse set of computing environments, optimizing model parameters and automating deployment have become an integral part of every such project (Kreuzberger et al., 2023). For this reason, multiple different MLOps tools have been developed to streamline and automate these procedures, among which the most popular and widely used are MLflow and Kubeflow. MLflow (MLflow-Org(Databricks), 2023) is an open source platform with an easy setup which covers important aspects of ML operations, offering tools for experiment tracking, reproducibility, model versioning and deployment, each a modular component that can be easily integrated to a third-party application. Kubeflow (Kubeflow, 2021) is an MLOps tool that runs on Kubernetes, a container orchestration service with resource allocation management features, which in turn makes the tool more agile for larger projects with a more complex computing environment.

In our case, conducting multiple experiments, i.e. multiple model trainings, becomes computationally intense and requires efficient resource scaling, making Kubeflow's contribution valuable. Apart from orchestrating machine learning workflows on Kubernetes clusters, Kubeflow provides end-to-end support for the entire ML lifecycle, including model training and especially hyperparameter tuning, which is pivotal in achieving the required performance. More specifically, Kubeflow utilizes Katib, a tool enabling automated hyperparameter selection and tuning using advanced AutoML techniques such as random search, grid search (Bergstra and Bengio, 2012) and Bayesian optimization (Snoek et al., 2012). In the broader MLOps landscape, although MLflow is widely adopted and highly modular, it lacks native integration with Kubernetes and does not offer the same level of support for scalable automated ML pipelines in production environments, making Kubeflow more robust for long-term solutions.

Figure 1 – The architecture of the proposed framework. The framework implements an end-to-end pipeline that spans from dataset creation and annotation to model training and inference. User interactions are managed through a web interface which provides options for data upload, training configuration and inference. Dataset creation is supported by the CVAT annotation tool, while experiment tracking and automated hyperparameter tuning are performed through Kubeflow and Katib. In the postprocessing phase, the best-performing model from each experiment is stored for subsequent inference.

Framework architecture

The proposed framework consists of multiple stages and extends beyond the specified task, and is designed with two main goals: 1) to provide a friendly and intuitive experience to non-technical users, and 2) to allow seamless expansion to support new tasks and additional annotation and MLOps tools. For these reasons, the architecture illustrated in Figure 1 is designed to be modular, allowing components to be added or switched to enhance or adapt functionality. The framework can be conveniently divided into two main parts based on their purpose: the *user interface* and the *backend system*.

User interface

To facilitate user interaction with the platform and the entire machine learning pipeline (data annotation, training, and inference), we developed a simple user interface based on the Flask web application framework (Pallets, 2024) with additional functionalities. This design allows users to avoid direct contact with programming code or the command line and instead use intuitive web pages with simplified forms, e.g., buttons, selection fields, to handle the data and conduct experiments. More specifically, through the interface, users can upload data and group them into datasets, which can then be reviewed as shown in Figure 2, where a summary of the dataset-related information, such as size, type and dimensions, is reported followed by a detailed table with its data information along with annotation actions and status in each row. Afterwards, users can access the "Train" page in Figure 3 and train an appropriate machine learning model on one of those datasets they created. Submitting the form will run a number of experiments, trying different model configurations via Katib, after which the one with the best results is stored in the database. Finally, as shown in Figure 4, they can access those trained models and utilize them for inference with newly uploaded images.

The screenshot shows the user interface for a dataset named "ZJULeaper Curated Subset". At the top, there is a navigation bar with "textailes" logo, "Collections Train ML Models", and a user profile "user@example.com". Below the title, there is a "Statistics" box showing: "No. of files: 2000", "No. annotated: 2000", and "Total size: 792MB". Below this, it says "Showing page 1 of 67 with 30 items (#1-30)" and "Page: 1 Go". The main content is a table with the following data:

#	Thumbnail	Name	Type	Size	Dimensions	Annotation status	Action
1		train/002675.jpg	2D Image	41 KB	512 x 512	Annotated	Annotate in CVAT
2		train/002685.jpg	2D Image	37 KB	512 x 512	Annotated	Annotate in CVAT
3		train/002686.jpg	2D Image	42 KB	512 x 512	Annotated	Annotate in CVAT
4		train/002687.jpg	2D Image	43 KB	512 x 512	Annotated	Annotate in CVAT
5		train/002689.jpg	2D Image	41 KB	512 x 512	Annotated	Annotate in CVAT

Figure 2 – The dataset page provides an overview of each image, including filename, type, size, annotation status and offers direct access to annotate images using CVAT.

Backend system

The backend system (on the right of the web framework) automates the execution of machine learning experiments and organizes the stored data. As shown in Figure 1, it is divided into three main branches: *dataset creation*, *training*, and *inference*, each one corresponding to an ML pipeline stage. Each branch integrates dedicated tools and operations that run independently, thus ensuring seamless data flow, experiment management, and inference. In the following, we provide an extensive analysis of each of these operations and how they are integrated within the platform.

Data annotation. Since dataset creation is a time-consuming process and requirements can vary across applications, the platform incorporates the CVAT annotator (CVAT.ai Corporation, 2023) to provide users with a fully-featured annotator, ready to support any computer vision task. Our framework has integrated the relevant CVAT services using its Python SDK (Software Development Kit), creating a direct link from our user interface to the annotator’s interface, where users can import their data and create annotations using a variety of selection tools such as brush tool, polygons, rectangles, cuboids, etc. Once the dataset preparation is complete, the annotations are automatically parsed by the platform to be used in a future training, or can be exported in different formats to meet the specific needs of the task.

Figure 3 – The training page allows users to select from the available machine learning models and datasets in order to proceed with model training.

Training. As illustrated in Figure 3, via the user interface (UI), users have the option to choose any or all models available to initiate training on an uploaded dataset. User input is translated via Flask into a YAML file, which is then sent to Kubeflow to initialize the experiments. Kubeflow, as a Kubernetes based project, analyzes the YAML file and creates multiple pods (application components allocated on shared resources) on the Kubernetes cluster to execute parallel experiments with different parameters. At this point, it is important to note that for hyperparameter tuning and experiment tracking, Kubeflow’s built-in tool Katib is utilized. Following a defined training strategy, the model attempts to modify parameters such as learning rate, batch size, number

of epochs, and momentum to maximize the target metric for the given task. Since the process produces multiple output files, including weights and configuration files, efficient file management is essential. The platform handles this by post-processing all outputs and only storing in its database the results from the run achieving the best score (according to the target metric).

Regarding the segmentation framework itself, it is based on the *Pytorch Segmentation (2019)* library, which is implemented in Python and primarily uses the PyTorch package. The framework is highly modular and configurable via JSON files, supporting a multitude of integrated services such as data augmentation and visualization utilities. It also includes a variety of deep learning models with multi-GPU support, allowing easy addition of new models, loss functions and custom dataset specifications. For training and visualization purposes, the ZJU-Leaper dataset (Zhang et al., 2021) was utilized as it contains a large number of samples from different fabric categories, along with masks for each image.

While the user is limited to selecting the model architecture, the operational parameters used for the training process are not exposed to the user. Specifically, the following components are managed exclusively via the system administrator's configuration:

- **Optimization Constraints:** The definition of the metric direction (e.g., maximizing mIoU) and stopping criteria.
- **Resource Allocation:** The assignment of computational resources, including GPU limits.
- **Trials Parallelization:** The number of parallel training trials executed simultaneously by the Kubeflow pipeline.

Inference

Description

Name: UNet
Trained on: ZJULeaper Curated Subset
mIoU Score: 71.3

Upload your images

No files selected.

Inference Results

Original Image	Model Output

Figure 4 – The inference page displays the predicted output of a selected machine learning model in comparison with the original input image.

Inference. With multiple trained machine learning models available in their collection, users can select the most suitable one, based on performance metrics and the specifics of their task, to perform inference on new data. The user interface prompts users to upload new data directly from their local computer to the platform. The uploaded data are then processed within a Docker container environment, which includes all the technical dependencies (the same Docker image as the one used for training can be used), and execute the inference routines. When completed, the result will be displayed on the same page, alongside the original image, as illustrated in Figure 4.

Discussion

Integrating machine learning into cultural heritage research significantly broadens investigative possibilities in the field, speeding up large datasets analysis and providing insights about them. The integration described in this paper bridges cultural heritage and machine learning through an easy-to-use framework, allowing cultural heritage researchers to have easy access to an end-to-end machine learning framework they can utilize for their work, opening new avenues for discovery and preservation. The framework is designed to be user-friendly and highly modular for easy adaptation on different project needs and requirements, making it a flexible asset against the many challenges faced in cultural heritage research. Also, thanks to its seamless integration with annotation tools like CVAT and its Kubernetes-based philosophy, the platform can be easily extended by integrating new computer vision tasks and algorithms, thus extending the potential of its applications, while also efficiently managing resources.

However, with the framework being centered around ML operations, there exist multiple challenges with hardware/GPU availability which is necessary for training ML models. In addition, the current implementation of the platform presents specific software limitations. A primary constraint is the inability to perform incremental learning; users cannot further train or fine-tune their models as new data become available. This is a significant drawback for the Cultural Heritage domain, where datasets are often limited in size and must be expanded gradually. Furthermore, the platform does not currently support multiclass segmentation, restricting workflows to binary tasks. Finally, the framework lacks automated data partitioning capabilities, necessitating that users manually split their datasets into training and validation sets before importing them. Future expansions of the framework's functionalities can address all the above constraints.

Focusing more on the future work and potential extensions of the platform, considerable opportunities exist for advancement in multiple directions. Concentrating on the technical attributes afforded by the platform, the framework can be enhanced through the integration of supplementary annotation tools to accommodate a broader range of data types, in addition to supporting further tasks, such as object detection, to facilitate the localization of defective areas. In addition, to further empower the framework's capabilities, we believe that there is great value in offering more advanced users the option to manually adjust training parameters when managing experiments, allowing greater control over the workflow. This direction would also open up the discussion on implementing user roles, where users would have different access levels depending on their permissions. Finally, to further improve efficiency, there is great potential in introducing an AI-guided annotator especially for the textiles domain, which can assist users by monitoring their modifications' history and suggesting similar annotations (Ravi et al., 2024) in other regions of the image.

Apart from technical improvements, the platform will also evolve through its practical use in real-life cultural heritage use cases, where its adaptability and resourcefulness will be tested against each problem’s intrinsic properties. With that in mind, we believe that it is essential for any planned future development or extension of the platform to keep adaptability and modularity in high priority, in order to ensure it will stay relevant in the long run to the problems it attempts to solve.

Appendix A. Experimental Setup and Evaluation

This section details the experimental protocol used to validate the proposed framework, including dataset preparation, hyperparameter optimization, and performance evaluation metrics.

A.1. Dataset and Preprocessing

To demonstrate the framework’s functionality, we utilized a subset of the ZJU-Leaper dataset. We randomly sampled 2000 instances to form a representative dataset. These instances were subsequently partitioned into training and validation sets using a 70/30 split ratio. It should be noted that the choice (complexity and quality) of the dataset is entirely determined by the user, with the model performance depending strongly on that. The framework itself has a strictly operational purpose and does not influence model performance on different datasets.

A.2. Training Framework and Hyperparameter Tuning

Upon the selection of a model architecture, in this experiment U-Net (Ronneberger et al., 2015), the system generates a YAML configuration file capturing the user’s specifications. This configuration is submitted to the KubeFlow pipeline to initiate the training process. The platform executes multiple independent trials to optimize model performance, selecting hyperparameters via an automated tuning algorithm (as detailed in the [Machine Learning Operations](#) section).

The optimization process terminates when one of the following stopping criteria is met:

- (1) The maximum defined number of trials is reached.
- (2) The target accuracy threshold is achieved.

The hyperparameters tuned during this process include the learning rate, batch size, and number of epochs. The search space for these parameters is defined within the ranges specified in the Table 1.

Table 1 – Hyperparameter search space configuration.

Hyperparameters	min	max
Learning Rate	10^{-5}	10^{-1}
Batch Size	2	64
Epochs	2	50

A.3. Evaluation Metric

Following the completion of the training trials, model performance is assessed using the mean Intersection over Union (mIoU) (Müller et al., 2022) metric, a standard for semantic segmentation. The mIoU value can be calculated with the following formula:

$$\text{mIoU} = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K \frac{TP_k}{TP_k + FP_k + FN_k}$$

where:

- K denotes the total number of classes.
- TP_k , FP_k , and FN_k represent the True Positives, False Positives, and False Negatives for class k respectively.

The optimization objective is set to maximize mIoU. The platform automatically retains the checkpoint from the specific trial that yields the highest mIoU score.

A.4. Results

Figure 5 illustrates the hyperparameter distribution and resulting metrics across multiple trials.

Figure 5 – The results and the hyperparameters for each of the training trials.

Quantitative results for a sample of three trials are presented in Table 2. In this experiment, Trial 1 achieved the optimal performance with an mIoU of 0.646.

Table 2 – Comparative results of experimental trials.

	Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 3
Learning Rate	6.5×10^{-2}	2.2×10^{-2}	2.7×10^{-2}
Batch Size	2	4	4
Epochs	4	3	3
mIoU	0.646	0.47	0.572

This process is identical when multiple models are involved. The only difference is that the platform searches across all models to identify and return the best-performing trial.

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Conflict of interest disclosure

The authors declare that they comply with the PCI rule of having no financial conflicts of interest in relation to the content of the article.

Data, script, code, and supplementary information availability

Scripts and code are available online: (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17062362>; Chatzisavvas, 2025).

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